

Upward Connecting Leader Initiation in Large-Area Photovoltaic Plants for Negative Lightning

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Abstract—This study investigate the conditions for the initiation of lightning upward connecting leaders (UCL) in large-area photovoltaic (PV) plants to enable the assessment of the most likely strike points on the PV array. The methodology, based on the Charge Simulation Method (CSM), is implemented in MATLAB, considering in-depth studies on lightning physics to describe the mechanism of the lightning strike with the necessary assumptions to simplify while maintaining a physically consistent model. The evaluation of possible UCL inception in the PV array is conducted by analyzing the electric field in the vicinity of the PV panels, a necessary condition for the formation of streamer corona discharges at the edges of the PV panels. To compare with a situation prior the erection of the PV plant, the analysis is also performed to the flat ground. In order to validate the results obtained with the implementation of the CSM, simulations based on the Finite Element Method (FEM) are performed to evaluate the electric field levels in the vicinity of the conductors, overcoming some limitations of the CSM due to the effect of proximity. With the support of the software Ansys Maxwell as a user-friendly interface for the FEM approach, the electric field at the leader tip and on the PV array structure is evaluated more consistently and the results are similar to those obtained by applying the CSM. In summary, this evaluation provides insights for studies on safeguarding large-area PV systems against lightning strikes, thereby advancing external lightning protection strategies in renewable energy infrastructure.

Keywords—large-area photovoltaic plants, electric field analysis, likely inception points of upward connecting leaders, Charge Simulation Method, Finite Element Method, external lightning protection

I. INTRODUCTION

Photovoltaic (PV) systems have become an increasingly important renewable energy source worldwide. Solar power represents the most economically attractive renewable energy and is widely accepted by the public, which ensures its potential for continued expansion in the coming years. Although PV panels are slightly elevated above the ground, large PV arrays can cover areas of square kilometers free of tall structures, making them exposed to direct lightning strikes. This susceptibility can result in damage from lightning, leading to higher maintenance costs and therefore longer amortization periods.

As an integral part of the power supply system, PV power plants must ensure a stable grid operation. To guarantee this

reliability, an efficient lightning protection system (LPS) has to be designed, which requires well coordinated components of the internal and external LPS. This components includes the air-termination system, the earth-termination system, the equipotential bonding and the surge protective devices (SPDs) for both electric and data systems of the power plant [1].

A. Air-Termination System

The installation of the lightning rods to protect the PV panels against direct strikes, aside from the material and installation costs, presents some challenges for the operation of the PV power plant. One challenge is the optimized arrangement of the lightning rods to avoid shadowing on the panels [2]. Another challenge is the eventual obstruction of the path of cleaning robots during the regular cleaning of the PV panels.

Due to the costs and challenges associated with the implementation of the air-termination system, some operators prefer to assume the risks of a direct lightning strike and the resulting replacement of the damaged panels. However, it is important to highlight that, besides protecting the PV array against direct strikes, the lightning rods provide dedicated paths for the lightning current to the earth-termination system [1]. These dedicated paths are fundamental as they prevent the transfer of lightning currents to the power system, thereby avoiding damage of other critical equipment like the inverters. Moreover, an efficient external LPS and earthing ensure sufficient energy dissipation, preventing SPDs from overstress [3].

B. Lightning Strikes on PV Arrays

In the event of a lightning strike to a hypothetical perfectly flat ground, one can consider the direct connection between the downward leader (DL) and the ground, assuming the absence of upward connecting leaders (UCLs). In this scenario, the striking distance to flat ground can be estimated from the distance between the DL tip and the ground when the final jump condition is reached between them, i.e., when the average potential gradient between them reaches critical values necessary for streamer development: 500 kV/m for positive streamers and 1000 kV/m – 2000 kV/m for negative ones [4].

For strikes on grounded structures, complexities arise that are typically disregarded in flat ground attractiveness analyses. Depending on the height of the structure, its connection with the downward leader occurs through an upward connecting leader incepted on the structure due to the intensification of the electric field at its extremities as the DL approaches. In elevated structures, connecting leaders are incepted long before the final jump condition is reached between the DL and these structures. In such cases, the connection is established between the upward and the downward leader. Thus, the striking distance to grounded structures could be defined as the separation between the end DL tip and the structure when a stable UCL is initiated from the latter. This definition considers that, once an stable UCL is initiated, the necessary conditions for its connection to the DL are satisfied. However this connection cannot be guaranteed, as multiple upward connecting leaders may appear on different parts of the structure, and usually, only one will successfully connect with the DL. Furthermore, a downward leader may connect directly to the ground, even if there are UCLs in a nearby grounded structure.

Therefore, the striking distance can be defined more consistently as the distance between the DL tip and the point of the structure from which arises the UCL, when the final jump condition between the two leaders is satisfied, i.e., when the average electric field between their extremities reaches the critical breakdown value. Assuming the breakdown is purely mediated by positive streamers, it is reasonable to consider a critical electric field of 500 kV/m [5].

When the attachment process considers the initiation and development of the upward connecting leader, the distance between the DL tip and the structure when the final jump condition is reached is greater than that estimated directly by the well-known electro-geometrical model (EGM). According to the EGM, the striking distance can be defined in a simplified way as the distance at which the final jump condition is established between the downward leader tip and the grounded structure, which is reasonable in the case of very low structures. For very low structures, the UCLs are initiated only when the separation between them and the DL almost corresponds to the striking distance defined by the EGM. Therefore, in this case, the presence of UCLs can be neglected, similar to the analysis of the striking distance to flat ground [4, 5].

This study proposes an evaluation of the conditions for UCL inception in a large-area ground-mounted PV system. The term "upward connecting leader", used throughout the text, refers to the upward leader initiated by the intensification of the electric field resulting from the approach of the downward stepped leader. This leader moves upwards towards the DL tip but does not necessarily imply that there will be a connection between them. Although PV panels are typically slightly elevated above the ground, the structure is complex in terms of the geometry of the modules distributed over a large area, where several UCLs may be incepted, as illustrated in the high-voltage laboratory experiment in Fig. 1. This evaluation aims to assess the likely UCL inception points for different configurations of

PV arrays, as well as the influence of the PV plant on the lightning activity at the site.

Fig. 1: Direct strike experiment on a PV array indicating the formation of UCLs at different points in the PV system. Photo: Courtesy of the Institute of High Voltage Engineering and System Performance of TU Graz. Experiment carried out at the Nikola Tesla Laboratory during the *OVE-Blitzschutztag 2024*

II. SIMULATION MODEL

Fig. 2 illustrates the model implemented for the electric field evaluation as the stepped leader extends downwards. The assumptions made to model each element are described as follows.

Fig. 2: Sketch of the proposed model to investigate the initiation of upward connecting leaders from PV array

A. Thundercloud and Ground Model

As discussed in [6], the extent of the negative charge region of the cloud is larger than the vertical distance to the ground, making it reasonable to represent the cloud base by a perfectly conducting plate which is larger than its height at a given

negative potential. From this configuration, it is simulated a uniform electric field between the cloud and the ground.

In this study, the thunderstorm cloud is modeled as perfectly conducting flat sheet of $10 \text{ km} \times 10 \text{ km}$, at an altitude of 4 km. The potential V_{cloud} , in MV, is calculated as a function of the prospective first return stroke peak current I_p , in kA, using Eq. (1) [4].

$$V_{cloud} = 5.86 \times 10^3 + 1.569 \times 10^3 I_p - 3.279 \cdot I_p^2 \quad (1)$$

The ground is represented by a perfectly conducting flat sheet of zero electric potential with the same dimensions, at 0 m. To allow for different charge densities along the cloud and ground flat sheets, in the MATLAB simulations, both are divided in small square plates with uniform surface charge density. The Charge Simulation Method (CSM) is applied to calculate the surface charge density of each plate, as described in Section II-D1. Although in this study the ground is modeled as a perfect conducting plate, the ground charges are modeled rather than simply applying the imaging method in order to allow further studies with different soil conditions.

B. PV Array Model

The PV array is modeled as a perfect conducting grounded structure (at zero potential), with charged surfaces of $120 \text{ m} \times 5 \text{ m}$ covering an area of one square kilometer with spaces of 10 m between columns or rows. The PV panels are placed at a mean height of 2 m, either parallel to the ground or inclined 24° , resembling a single-axis tracking system. The PV panels are also divided into small square plates of $40 \text{ m} \times 5 \text{ m}$, each with a uniform surface charge density.

C. Downward Stepped Leader Model

The downward leader is assumed to be a vertical lossy conductor of cylindrical geometry with a hemispherical tip extending downwards. The charge distribution ρ_l , in C/m, along the stepped leader as it extends towards the ground is calculated as a function of the prospective first return stroke peak current I_p , in kA, following the model introduced by [6], as shown in Eq. (2), valid for $z_0 \geq 10 \text{ m}$.

$$\rho_l(z') = a_0 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{z'}{H - z_0}\right) \cdot G(z_0) \cdot I_p + \frac{I_p \cdot (a + bz')}{1 + cz' + dz'^2} \cdot H(z_0) \quad (2)$$

$$G(z_0) = 1 - \frac{z_0}{H} \quad (3)$$

$$H(z_0) = 0.3e^{-(z_0 - 10)/75} + 0.7G(z_0) \quad (4)$$

where:

z' - length along the DL starting from its tip, in m;

z_0 - height of the leader tip above ground, in m;

H - height of the origin of the DL in the cloud from the ground level, in m;

$a_0 = 1.476 \times 10^{-5}$; $a = 4.857 \times 10^{-5}$;

$b = 3.9097 \times 10^{-6}$; $c = 0.522$; $d = 3.73 \times 10^{-3}$.

The charge distribution obtained from the Eq. (2) is approximately linear along a significant length of the DL. However, due to the effect of the ground (and grounded structures) and the field enhancement at the leader tip, there is an abrupt increase in the accumulated charge near to the DL tip [6].

The DL potential is calculated at its surface by the CSM, in which its radius is estimated considering the external electric field of the corona sheath equal to 1500 kV/m [6].

The equivalent model of the descending leader in the Finite Element Method (FEM) is simulated as a cylinder with the same radius and hemispherical tip, whose charge density, in C/m³, is also given by Eq. (2) divided by the cross-section of the DL.

As a simplification on the real dynamic conditions imposed by the development of the DL, the methodology of this study is based on an electrostatic-by-step approach. This means that the calculation of the static electric field is performed for different leader lengths, as different electrostatic conditions of the DL are reached during its stepped propagation. An electrostatic-by-steps approach is reasonable before the initiation and propagation of UCLs.

Since this study investigates the electric field conditions to UCL inception from the flat ground and non-elevated structures, the evaluation considers negative downward flashes only.

D. Calculation Methods

The simulations based on the CSM are performed in MATLAB and validated through the software Ansys Maxwell, which employs the FEM.

1) *Charge Simulation Method*: The CSM is used to calculate the potential at any point of the simulation domain due to the contribution of all the represented charge distributions, i.e., the equivalent surface charges of the cloud, ground and PV array, as well as the DL line charges. This is achieved by solving the system of linear equations indicated in Eq. (5), which is derived from Poisson's equation, considering the corresponding boundary conditions.

$$[\Phi] = [P][Q] \quad (5)$$

where:

Φ - potential vector comprising the sub-vectors of potential points corresponding to each element of the simulation domain (cloud, ground, PV array and DL), in V;

P - matrix of potential coefficients obtained from the analytical formulations that depend on the configuration and position of the equivalent charges and potential points;

Q - equivalent charge density vector comprising the sub-vectors corresponding to each element of the simulation domain, in C/m or C/m², depending on the charge configuration (line or surface).

The CSM is advantageous for its applicability to three-dimensional field problems without axial symmetry [7], making it common in studies on the development of the leader channel [6, 8, 9].

The first step of the CSM in this study is to calculate the equivalent cloud, ground and PV array surface charges from the known potential values. These charges are placed outside the domain where the potential and electric field distribution are calculated. Once the equivalent charges are determined, the potential and field strength can be assessed anywhere in the simulation domain, using the analytical formulations for the potential coefficients corresponding to any configuration of charge distribution (line or surface) and the superposition principle. As the charge distribution of the leader changes by step, it is calculated in every simulation step and its effect on the other elements is re-evaluated, ensuring that all the charge distributions are adjusted to maintain the boundary conditions satisfied.

The challenge of the CSM lies in the optimal number and placement of the equivalent charges and potential points to avoid an ill-conditioned matrix and unnecessary computational costs, especially when the desired potential points are located close to the extremities of the objects. The implementation in MATLAB is advantageous as it can be easily and automatically replicated for different lightning parameters (peak current) and geometries.

2) *Finite Element Method*: To compare the results obtained from the CSM and ensure consistency, simulations are also performed using the FEM by means of the software Ansys Maxwell. This method is well suited to problems with complex geometries and provides a more detailed and accurate representation of the electric field distribution, overcoming some limitations of the CSM due to proximity effect. The same geometric configurations and boundary conditions used in the CSM are applied to the FEM model. The simulation domain in FEM was therefore adjusted to maintain the boundary conditions satisfied.

The basic idea of FEM is to divide the simulation domain in small interconnected elements [7]. The challenge in this case is to generate an optimized fine mesh with sufficient precision to capture the variations in the electric field near the objects without excessive computational costs. Therefore finer meshes are modeled at the vicinity of the DL tip and the PV panels, especially near those close to the leader's region of influence.

E. Simulation Setups

To evaluate the likely UCL inception points in the PV array and the influence of the PV plant on the lightning activity at the site, the following different setups are simulated.

The main objective of this study is to evaluate the electric field conditions in large-area photovoltaic systems, which justifies the extensive simulation domain. As this is an initial study, in all the simulation setups, the DL is located in the center of the simulation domain, though the model allows for positioning the DL at any place in the domain. Thus, even though the entire domain is simulated using both calculation methodologies, the evaluations are focused on the central region near the DL tip, where the electric field is more intense and more favorable for UCL inception.

1) *Flat Ground Only*: To compare with a situation prior to the erection of the PV plant, the evaluation of the electric field between the DL tip and the flat ground is also performed. Since upward connecting leaders are not expected to emanate from a perfectly flat ground, an average electric field value of 1500 kV/m, necessary for negative streamer propagation, is adopted as the critical electric field for the breakdown of the gap between the leader tip and the ground in the striking distance estimation.

2) *PV Panels Parallel to the Ground*: In this setup, the PV panels are modeled as being parallel to the ground at a mean height of 2 m. This configuration helps to evaluate how the presence of PV panels, even without any inclination, affects the electric field distribution and the likelihood of UCL inception points.

3) *Inclined PV Panels*: In this setup, the PV panels are inclined at an angle of 24° maintaining a mean height of 2 m. This configuration aims to assess the impact of panel inclination on the electric field distribution and the potential UCL inception points. Inclined panels can create different electric field enhancement regions compared to flat panels, thus influencing the likelihood of UCLs.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first step to adjust the boundaries of the FEM simulation domain is the comparison of the background potential due to the cloud and ground charges only. Fig. 3 shows the comparison between FEM and CSM for a cloud potential $V_{cloud} = -50$ MV, corresponding to a peak current $I_p = 30$ kA.

Fig. 3: Vertical potential profile along Z axis due to the cloud and ground charges only

To enable a direct comparison of the simulation setups, all the results presented correspond to the same situation in which the DL tip is at a height of 50 m, and the cloud and leader parameters are calculated for a prospective first return stroke peak current $I_p = 30$ kA.

A. Flat Ground Only

This section present the results obtained for a configuration without the PV array. Fig. 4 shows the charge distributions on

the cloud and ground surfaces and the linear charge density of the downward leader calculated using the CSM. It is notable the intensification of the ground charge distribution in the region of influence of the DL within a radius of approximately 500 m around the z-axis, where the leader develops vertically. Therefore, the results are more accurate when the size of the charge surfaces on the ground is smaller within this region.

Fig. 4: Equivalent surface charge distributions on the cloud and ground, in $\mu\text{C}/\text{m}^2$, and linear charge distribution on downward leader, in mC/m

Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 present, respectively, the potential and electric field distribution on the plane YZ, obtained by the FEM simulations. From the potential distribution of Fig. 5 it is possible to see the abrupt change of the potential close to the leader tip due to the proximity to the ground with zero potential, which implies in a region of intense electric field between the DL tip and the ground, as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 5: Potential distribution between thundercloud and flat ground along the plane YZ of the simulation domain

The vertical electric field profiles along the gap between the DL tip and ground (z -axis) obtained through CSM and FEM are illustrated in Fig. 7. A significant increase in the electric field is noticed close to the extremity of the leader, especially in the results obtained through the FEM simulations. The difference between the results near the DL tip can be explained by the representation of the leader charges in each simulation. In Ansys Maxwell, it is modeled as a volume of charges and the potential is calculated directly at its surface. In MATLAB, the line charges are placed in the center of the

Fig. 6: Electric field distribution around downward leader along the plane YZ of the simulation domain

leader and the potential is calculated at its radius, i.e., 2.9 m apart for this charged line.

Fig. 7: Vertical electric field profile along the gap between DL tip and ground

Table I shows the average electric field between the DL tip and the flat ground. In both situations, the average electric field is below the critical value 1500 kV/m , which means that the final jump condition from ground to DL tip is not reached when the leader tip is at 50 m.

TABLE I
AVERAGE ELECTRIC FIELD ALONG THE GAP BETWEEN THE DOWNWARD LEADER TIP AND THE FLAT GROUND

Critical E-Field	CSM	FEM
1500 kV/m	564 kV/m	659 kV/m

B. PV Panels Parallel to the Ground

Fig. 8 shows the charge distributions on the ground and PV array surfaces and the linear charge density of the downward leader calculated using the CSM. Fig. 9 provides a detailed view of the regions where the charge distribution on the PV panels intensifies due to the presence of the DL at the center region.

Fig. 8: Equivalent surface charge distributions on the ground and PV panels, in $\mu\text{C}/\text{m}^2$, and linear charge distribution on the downward leader, in mC/m

Fig. 9: Equivalent surface charge distributions on the ground and PV panels, in $\mu\text{C}/\text{m}^2$, and linear charge distribution on the downward leader, in mC/m , zoom of the central region

Fig. 10 presents the electric field distribution on the plane YZ, obtained from the FEM simulations. When comparing the electric field distribution with the situation before the erection of the PV system (Fig. 6), the influence of the PV panels on the electric field at ground level is noticeable. Since the PV panels are modeled as grounded structures, the abrupt change from zero potential to high potential due to the DL development results in a higher electric field level in the vicinity of the PV panels, especially at the edges.

A more detailed visualization of the electric field on the PV surface and around the downward leader tip is provided by Fig. 11. In order to improve the accuracy of the results in the region of greatest influence of the leader, the FEM calculation mesh is more refined in the vicinity of the panels located in the center. The black line indicates the reference axis for calculating the electric field between the DL tip and the PV panel, shown in Fig. 12. The same reference is adopted in the CSM calculation. Despite the good agreement between the results, the results obtained using FEM again indicate a more intense electric

field near the tip of the leader, as well as near the corner of the PV panel.

Fig. 10: Electric field distribution around downward leader and grounded PV panels along the plane YZ of the simulation domain

Fig. 11: Electric field distribution around downward leader and grounded PV panels

Table II shows the average electric field between the DL tip and the corner of the PV panel. In both simulations, the average electric field is over the critical value $500\text{ kV}/\text{m}$ for positive streamers. If one assumes the EGM definition of striking distance, the condition for electric breakdown is reached in this case. Since long connecting leaders are not expected in slightly elevated structures such as the simulated large PV array, it can be reasonable to disregard the inception and development of stable UCL in this case. However, for a more accurate evaluation of the possible striking points on the complex arrangement of the PV array, the UCL inception conditions are to be evaluated through the criteria discussed in Section I-B.

C. Inclined PV Panels

Fig. 13 shows the electric field on the PV array surface, along a plane placed at the highest edge of the modules,

Fig. 12: Electric field profile along the gap between DL tip and PV panel

TABLE II
AVERAGE ELECTRIC FIELD ALONG THE GAP BETWEEN THE DOWNWARD LEADER TIP AND THE PV PANEL

Critical E-Field	CSM	FEM
500 kV/m	548 kV/m	678 kV/m

and around the downward leader tip, for a situation in which the panels are inclined at 24° . The black line indicates the reference axis for calculating the electric field between the DL tip and the PV panel, shown in Fig. 14. The results presented in this section correspond to the FEM simulations.

Fig. 13: Electric field distribution around downward leader and grounded PV panels inclined 24°

Although the corners of the inclined PV panels are slightly elevated compared to the panels parallel to the ground, the average electric field between the DL tip and the PV panel corner does not change significantly. However, it is worth to notice an intensification of the electric field at the beginning of the curve in Fig. 14, i.e., in the vicinity of the PV modules.

IV. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In spite of being an initial study on the electric field conditions for UCL inception on large-area PV arrays, this study already presents some important considerations, including the

Fig. 14: Vertical electric field profile along the gap between DL tip and inclined PV panel

modeling and evaluation of a truly large-scale configuration of PV panels. The main findings and observations from this evaluation are summarized as follows:

- The erection of PV panels alters the electric field distribution compared to the flat ground scenario. The presence of grounded PV panels introduces abrupt changes in potential, leading to higher electric field levels, especially around the panel corners (and edges). In addition, the presence of grounded structures is favorable for the development of positive streamers, which consequently favors the initiation of UCLs.
- FEM simulations: the use of Ansys Maxwell provides a user-friendly interface that facilitates the setup and execution of complex simulations. The FEM offers better accuracy in calculating the electric field, especially in the vicinity of objects, by employing a refined mesh in these areas. This allows for a more precise representation of potential and electric field distributions around complex geometries such as PV panels.
- CSM simulations: the CSM demonstrated good agreement with the FEM simulations, but requires more carefully performed analyses at tips, corners and edges of the objects to be effective in this type of study. The simulations by CSM have the great advantage of simply altering the simulated geometry and the object parameters, such as the cloud potential and the stepped leader charge distribution as functions of the prospective return stroke peak current. However, each type of equivalent charge distribution requires a specific function for calculating the potential coefficients. The CSM requires careful optimization of the placement and number of points for potential calculation, as well as the distribution of equivalent charges. This can be challenging but is crucial for achieving accurate results while avoiding excessive computational costs.

Further simulations are under development to improve the accuracy of the CSM simulations for different PV array setups and to incorporate a model for the inception of stable UCLs.

This will provide a more comprehensive understanding of the conditions leading to UCL formation and, consequently, allow the assessment of the most likely strike points of the PV array. The current study is focused on a downward leader positioned at the center of the simulation domain, but the simulation model also allows for exploring different DL positions to evaluate the impact on UCL inception across various parts of the PV array. Additionally, future work can consider different peak currents to enable a complete striking distance evaluation as a function of this engineering parameter.

In conclusion, this study lays the groundwork for further investigations into lightning strikes in large-area PV arrays. The findings highlight the importance of using accurate simulation methods due to the geometric complexity of a PV array, as well as the need for further analysis including stable UCL inception models to ensure the identification of the most likely impact points and allow specific recommendations for lightning protection and the reliability of PV systems.

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